

Bioconjugates from smart polymers and β -galactosidase: Synthesis, characterization and application in producing galacto-oligosaccharides from lactose

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Manuscript received 15 June 2018, accepted 25 June 2018

This paper summarizes two earlier published works^{1,2} on synthesis, characterization of smart (thermo-responsive) bioconjugate and its application for synthesis of galacto-oligosaccharides (GOS). It is known that the native enzyme in homogenous solution provides maximum utilization of substrate. But, it has several drawbacks. Again immobilization of enzyme on solid support has advantages like continuous mode operation, enzyme reutilization etc. But it also suffers from drawbacks like diffusional problem. Hence, the concept smart bioconjugate was conceived. Accordingly, smart/responsive bioconjugate was synthesized by copolymerization with modified β -galactosidase and *N*-isopropylacrylamide (NIPAAm). The various properties of the synthesized bioconjugate were estimated and compared with native enzyme and a non-responsive bioconjugate, polyacrylamide- β -galactosidase (PA β G). The process of bioconjugation decreases the lower critical solution temperature (LCST). The effects of various operating parameters (temperature, pH, organic solvent etc.) on enzyme activity were tested. The poly-NIPAAm- β -galactosidase (PN β G) bioconjugate showed much-improved operational, thermal, storage stabilities and less sensitivity towards variation in pH. The addition of ethylene glycol (up to 20% v/v) enhanced the activity of PN β G with no loss in stability; however; the trend reversed with the addition of ethanol.

Furthermore, the thermo-responsive PN β G bioconjugate was utilized for the synthesis of GOS from lactose. A maximum GOS yield of 35% (on dry basis) was observed at 100 g/L ILC and 0.275 mg/mL (0.055 U/mL) conjugated protein. The operating parameters (initial lactose concentration (ILC), bioconjugate concentration, temperature etc.) on GOS synthesis were also investigated. Finally, the apparent kinetic parameters were estimated from an earlier developed five-step, nine-parameter kinetic model, and the simulated results (using COPASI) excellently matched with the experimental data.

Keywords: Enzyme immobilization, bioconjugate, responsive polymer, galacto-oligosaccharide, kinetic model, smart polymer.

1. Introduction

The immobilization of biocatalyst has received a great attention for its use both in research as well as industrial-scale enzymatic processes. Enzyme under native-state offers maximum conversion of reactant but suffers from several limitations like difficulty to separate and reuse of the enzyme, inability to use in continuous process, lower stability of enzyme etc. Enzyme immobilization is necessary to overcome the difficulties associated with free enzyme and to get better product quality^{3,4}.

General techniques for immobilization are entrapment, gelification, physical adsorption, ionic binding, covalent bind-

ing or cross-linking⁵. Immobilization by adsorption offers better opportunity to reuse supports after simple washing because of weak binding forces with support, but chances of enzyme leakage⁶ is much higher than other techniques. On the other hand, cross-linking provides better enzyme stability⁷ and hence less chances of enzyme leakage.

A wide variety of solid supports, such as ion-exchange resin, merckogel⁸, chitosan beads^{9,10}, agarose beads¹¹, graphite¹² and cotton cloth¹³, and polymeric membranes have been reported in the literature^{3,4,14} for the immobilization of enzyme. Because of solid support, enzymes are confined in a particular space in the reactor. However, immobi-

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lization on solid support poses several limitations like resistances for diffusion of reactants and products, loss in enzyme activity during immobilization, increase in reaction time, and membrane fouling¹⁵. The diffusional problem is the main disadvantage of immobilization on solid support.

The concept of smart polymer/responsive/reversible polymer may overcome the disadvantages associated with solid support^{1,2,16}. They have recently received a great deal of attention from researchers for the applications to the fields of biotechnology, medicine, and engineering¹⁷⁻¹⁹. Responsive polymers show very fast response to slight changes in environmental stimuli such as pH, temperature, and ionic strength and regain their previous states as the stimuli are removed²⁰. Thermo-responsive polymer (where temperature acts as stimulus) undergo a reversible phase change from soluble to insoluble or vice versa with slight change in temperature around the lower critical solution temperature (LCST)²⁰. Several polymers have been reported to show thermo-responsive properties, such as poly-*N*-isopropylacrylamide (PNIPAAm; LCST: ~32°C), poly-*N*-vinyl-caprolactam (LCST: 31–37°C), *PN,N*-diethyl-acrylamide (LCST: 32–34°C), poly-acrylic acid-co-acrylamide (LCST: 25°C), and poly-*N*-ethyl-oxazoline (LCST: 62°C)^{21,22}. The PNIPAAm is the most preferred and widely studied thermo-responsive polymer²³⁻²⁵ owing to its solubility in water, sharpness of phase transition around its LCST (32°C), and easy separation from the solution phase by the addition of salt or surfactants above the LCST²⁶. Bioconjugates of such thermo-responsive polymers can be synthesized by copolymerization with enzymes^{27,28}. Such bioconjugate is expected to impose negligible mass transfer limitations on the substrate and products¹⁶ because of soluble property below its LCST. It was also noticed from the literature that the LCST of PNIPAAm is almost independent of the concentration or molecular weight²⁹. Furthermore, PNIPAAm-based bioconjugates have LCST close to normal human body temperature, which is the optimum temperature for most enzymes³⁰.

Galacto-oligosaccharides (GOS) are important nutraceuticals and regarded as prebiotic food ingredient. GOS is a complex mixture of tri-, tetra-, penta-saccharides etc. up to degree of polymerization of 10. In the next few decades, GOS could be one of the most important and essential products in daily-life. The main applications of GOS are as food supplement for the lactose-intolerant people (especially diabetic patients) and infant foods. In addition to this, GOS can be

used in a variety of products, including fermented milk products, breads, jams, confectionery, and beverages with a certain limit. However, excessive consumption of GOS may lead to harmful side effects for human being³¹. Hence, the market of oligosaccharides is rapidly expanding. Recently, very few companies world-wide have started producing GOS in commercial scale; however, with lesser purity³².

The GOS may be synthesized via enzymatic action of β -galactosidase (EC 3.2.1.23) on lactose³³. The β -galactosidase enzyme converts lactose via two simultaneous reactions: the trans-galactosylation reaction, which produces GOS; and the hydrolysis reaction, which forms glucose and galactose^{34,35}. Hence, the product mixture always contains unreacted lactose, GOS, glucose and galactose.

This paper is a summary of earlier published works^{1,2}. The objective of the present work was to study the efficacy of PNIPAAm- β -galactosidase (PN β G) bioconjugate for GOS synthesis. Smart bioconjugates were synthesized and characterized. In this regard, studying the change in properties of PNIPAAm- β -galactosidase compared to the native enzyme and the enzyme conjugated with non-responsive polyacrylamide (PAAm) would be of interest. It was also thought to study the operating parameters on enzyme activity as well as on GOS production. An earlier developed five-step, nine-parameter kinetic model⁴ was tested. The apparent kinetic parameters were estimated using the genetic algorithm of the COPASI package and the experimental results were validated with the simulated results.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Synthesis of PNIPAAm- β -galactosidase bioconjugate

The bioconjugates were synthesized in a two-steps process. In the first step, the enzyme was modified using itaconic anhydride to introduce an acrylic group on enzyme. The extent of enzyme modification was calculated by estimating the free amino groups as per eq. (1).

$$\text{Modification (\%)} = [1 - (A_{\text{mod}}/A_{\text{nat}})] \times 100 \quad (1)$$

where, A_{mod} and A_{nat} represent the absorbance values of the modified and native enzymes, respectively.

In the second step, the bioconjugate was synthesized by the copolymerization between NIPAAm monomer and modified β -galactosidase using *N,N,N',N'*-tetra-methylethylenediamine (TEMED) as catalyst and ammonium persulphate (APS) as initiator¹. Using same procedure, a non-respon-

sive polyacrylamide- β -galactosidase (PA β G) bioconjugate was also synthesized in order to compare the properties of the bioconjugates. Detail procedure and reaction scheme are mentioned elsewhere^{1,2,16}. Bioconjugate yield and specific loading were defined as per eqs. (2) and (3), respectively^{1,16}.

Bioconjugate yield (%) =

$$\frac{\text{Amount of protein conjugated polymer}}{\text{Modified protein taken}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Specific loading} = \frac{\text{Amount of conjugated protein}}{\text{Mass of dry polymer}} \quad (3)$$

2.2. Estimation of lower critical solution temperature

LCST is the temperature below which the polymer remains in soluble state and above which the polymer separates out from the solution. The LCSTs of both the PN β G bioconjugate and PNIPAAm polymer were estimated by observing the change in absorbance at 450 nm in the presence and absence of NaCl and lactose using the UV-Vis spectrophotometer¹⁶. A sharp change in phase indicates the LCST.

2.3. Determination of molecular weight

Various types of molecular weights of the bioconjugates and PNIPAAm polymer were estimated using gel permeation chromatography (GPC) employing a bank of 3 columns and tetrahydrofuran (THF) as mobile phase. The detail procedure is presented elsewhere¹.

2.4. Enzyme assay

The activity of enzyme was estimated using *o*-nitrophenyl- β -D-galactopyranoside (ONPG) as substrate. The amount of protein was estimated by bicinchoninic acid method. The detail procedure is reported earlier^{1,2}.

2.5. GOS synthesis

GOS was synthesized from lactose using the PN β G bioconjugate under batch mode with a stirring. Total volume of the reaction mixture was 25 mL. The reaction was carried out under conditions of varying ILC (50–200 g/L), conjugated protein concentrations (0.14–0.40 mg/mL), and temperatures (30–50°C) in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 6).

2.6. HPLC analysis

The concentration of reaction mixture were estimated using HPLC as per method reported earlier².

3. Results and discussion

3.1. LCST determination

The LCST of 1.5% (w/v) PNIPAAm was found to be 32.5°C, and it is independent of the polymer concentration. However, the LCST of 1.5% (w/v) PNIPAAm polymer and bioconjugate decreased in the presence of 0.05 M NaCl (Fig. 1). The LCST of the PN β G bioconjugate is dependent on concentration of bioconjugate and decreased as compared to that of the PNIPAAm polymer¹. The conjugation of modified β -galactosidase with PNIPAAm probably increased the hydrophobicity of the bioconjugate and hence reduction in the LCST²⁰. Furthermore, addition of salt increased the ionic strength of the solution and hence decreased the charge repulsion between the polymer or bioconjugate molecules, which facilitated the precipitation of the polymer or bioconjugate²⁴.

Fig. 1. Lower critical solution temperature of PNIPAAm polymer and PNIPAAm- β -galactosidase bioconjugate.

3.2. Determination of molecular weight

Different types of molecular weights such as the weight-average (M_w), number-average (M_n), and Z-average (M_z) molecular weights of PNIPAAm polymer and PN β G bioconjugate were estimated through GPC. The polydispersity index was then calculated from eq. (4) to understand the molecular weight distributions. The estimated values are mentioned in Table 1.

$$\text{Polydispersity index (PDI)} = \frac{M_w}{M_n} \quad (4)$$

Table 1. Molecular weights of PNIPAAm polymer and PNIPAAm- β -galactosidase bioconjugate

Polymer/Bioconjugate	M_w (kDa)	M_n (kDa)	M_z (kDa)	PDI
PNIPAAm polymer	162	120	220	1.35
PNIPAAm- β -galactosidase	595	406	913	1.46

M_w – Weight average MW, M_n – Number average MW, M_z – Z average MW.

The PDI values clearly showed that a wide range of molecular weights for both polymer and bioconjugates was obtained because of radical uncontrolled polymerization¹⁶.

3.3. Effect of parameters on activity of bioconjugates

3.3.1. Effect of temperature

The effect of temperature on the catalytic activity of bioconjugates and the native enzyme was investigated at varying temperatures (20–80°C) using ONPG as the substrate. The values were presented with respect to the maximum values (taken as 100%). The activities of all three enzyme preparations increased with the temperature up to 60°C; the activities of the PA β G bioconjugate and native enzyme then decreased. On the other hand, the activity of the PN β G bioconjugate increased up to 70°C and then started to decrease (data not shown)¹.

3.3.2. Effect of pH

Each enzyme has an optimum pH value where it shows maximum activity. The PN β G bioconjugate showed a broad pH profile around 4.5–7.0 signifying their less sensitivity to pH variation than its native form (Fig. 2)¹. In addition, the similar kind of stability profile was observed in all three cases. This may be attributed to the change in pH value around the active sites of the bioconjugates by polymer support. The interaction (electrostatic or hydrophobic) between molecular species in solution and support matrix changed the microenvironment of the active sites of the enzyme^{1,36}.

3.3.3. Effect of organic solvent

The presence of various organic solvents may change the activity and stability of the enzyme, depending on the nature of the enzyme and organic solvents³⁷. PN β G bioconjugate and native β -galactosidase were tested in the presence of varying concentrations of ethylene glycol (EG) and ethanol in an aqueous medium¹. The change in enzyme activity in the presence of ethanol and EG is represented in Fig. 3. The activity of both the native β -galactosidase and

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on enzyme activity at 30°C. The maximum values (PNIPAAm- β -galactosidase: 0.09 U/mL, PAAm- β -galactosidase: 0.10 U/mL, and native β -galactosidase: 0.15 U/mL) were taken as 100%.

Fig. 3. Effect of organic solvents (ethylene glycol and ethanol) on enzyme activity. The activities of β -galactosidase solution without organic solvent were considered as 100%.

PN β G bioconjugate increased with the EG concentration up to 20% (v/v) and then decreased slightly. On the other hand, the activity of PN β G bioconjugate decreased gradually with increasing ethanol concentration; no such change was observed for the native enzyme. Both enzyme preparations showed much better stability in EG than in ethanol¹. This may be due to the change in hydrophobicity around the active site of the enzyme in the presence of organic solvent and the denaturation capacity of the solvents. DC is a rela-

tive measure of the denaturing tendency of different organic solvents.

3.4. Storage stability

The long-term storage stabilities of the bioconjugates and native enzyme were monitored by keeping the respective solutions at 20°C for 30 days. The activities were estimated at regular interval of time using ONPG method¹. It was found that the PN β G and PA β G bioconjugates retained ~68% and ~72% of the initial activity after 30 days. However, the native enzyme lost its activity sharply beyond 10 days and became zero within 20 days. At low temperatures (i.e. below the LCST), both PNIPAAm and PAAm polymers form a protective layer over the enzyme which resists denaturation of protein³⁸.

3.5. Thermal stability

The enzyme may become unstable at higher temperatures and after long run times. Therefore, the thermal stability of the PN β G bioconjugate was tested by incubating a solution of PN β G in phosphate buffer (pH 6) at four different temperatures (30, 40, 45 and 50°C). Residual enzyme activity was tested at 30°C at regular intervals with ONPG as the substrate². The values are presented with respect to initial enzyme activity (considered as 100%). As anticipated, the stability of PN β G bioconjugate was highest at 30°C and lowest at 50°C. The PN β G bioconjugate retained ~90% of its initial activity after incubation for 100 h at 30°C; the activity levels dropped to ~80%, 50% and ~43% at 40, 45, and 50°C, respectively. Furthermore, the rate of deactivation of the enzyme was very fast at 50°C, where it lost approximately 38% of its initial activity during the first 10 h of incubation (Fig. 4).

3.6. GOS synthesis using bioconjugate

Under conditions of 100 g/L ILC, 0.275 mg/mL conjugated protein, pH 6 and 40°C, a maximum GOS yield of 35% (on dry basis) was observed, along with yields of 13% and 1% for glucose and galactose, respectively and 51% unreacted lactose². A time course concentrations profile of lactose utilization and GOS formation is presented in Fig. 5.

3.7. Effect of operating parameters on GOS synthesis

3.7.1. Effect of initial lactose concentration

It was thought to test the effect of ILC on GOS synthesis. Accordingly, GOS yield was evaluated under varying ILCs and a constant conjugated protein concentration (0.27 mg/

Fig. 4. Thermal stability of PNIPAAm- β -galactosidase bioconjugate in phosphate buffer of pH 6 at various temperatures. The initial activities of the respective cases were taken as 100%.

Fig. 5. Time-course composition of the reaction mixture at 100 g/L of initial lactose concentration, 0.275 mg/mL (0.055 U/mL) conjugated protein, pH 6 and 40°C.

mL). It may be noted that GOS yield remained approximately the same for 50 and 100 g/L of ILC, and decreased thereafter (Fig. 6). Furthermore, the yields of both glucose and galactose decreased when the ILC was increased (for more detail Ref. [2]). This may be attributed to the predominance of the trans-galactosylation activity of the enzyme over the hydrolysis activity^{4,13}. At higher lactose concentrations the formation of monosaccharides was lower which is desirable.

3.7.2. Effect of enzyme concentration

The effect of bioconjugate concentration on GOS yield was evaluated by varying the concentration of conjugated protein (range, 0.14–0.40 mg/mL). As the enzyme concen-

Fig. 6. Effect of initial lactose concentration on GOS yield at various temperatures, 0.275 mg/mL conjugated protein and pH 6.

tration was increased, the equilibrium of formation of GOS increased and eventually attained a plateau beyond a certain concentration (0.275 mg/mL) of conjugated protein. Nevertheless, compared to low enzyme concentrations, the maximum GOS yield was achieved relatively faster at high enzyme concentrations (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Effect of enzyme concentration on GOS yield at various initial lactose concentrations, pH 6 and 40°C.

3.7.3. Effect of temperature

Formation of GOS was investigated at four different temperatures (30, 40, 45 and 50°C) with 50 and 100 g/L of ILC and 0.275 mg/mL of conjugated protein. The result is presented in Fig. 8. The rate of formation of GOS was also calculated at the initial phase of the reaction (after 1 h), when it was anticipated that most of the enzyme remained active (refer Table 2 for values). This clearly suggests that although temperature has a favorable effect on GOS yield, enzyme stability decreases on prolonged exposure to high temperatures.

culated at the initial phase of the reaction (after 1 h), when it was anticipated that most of the enzyme remained active (refer Table 2 for values). This clearly suggests that although temperature has a favorable effect on GOS yield, enzyme stability decreases on prolonged exposure to high temperatures.

Fig. 8. Effect of temperature on GOS yield at two different initial lactose concentrations (50 and 100 g/L), 0.275 mg/mL of conjugated protein and pH 6.

Table 2. Initial rate of formation of GOS at various temperature and initial lactose concentration with 0.275 mg/mL conjugated protein and pH 6

Temperature (°C)	Initial reaction rate ^a (mM GOS/h)	
	At 50 g/L of ILC	At 100 g/L of ILC
30	1.206±0.060	1.534±0.075
40	1.734±0.085	4.329±0.173
45	2.366±0.106	5.049±0.182
50	1.944±0.087	3.192±0.120

^aInitial reaction rate was calculated on the basis of GOS (tri-saccharide) formation after 1 h.

3.8. Reusability test

To determine the maximum number of cycles for which the PNβG bioconjugate could be reutilized for GOS synthesis, 10 successive runs were carried out with 50 g/L of ILC and 0.275 mg/mL of conjugated protein (at pH 6 and 40°C). It was observed that after an initial decrease in the first 3–4 cycles, GOS yield remained approximately the same in successive cycles. Interestingly, it was observed that after the 10th cycle, the bioconjugate could still produce ~10% yield of GOS. This observation implies that the PNβG bioconjugate

may be re-used for several consecutive runs (Ref. [2] for detail).

2.7. Kinetic model and simulation

An earlier developed five-step, nine-parameter kinetic model (eqs. (5)–(9)) was tested for the present study⁴. The parameters were estimated and simulated results (using COPASI)³⁹ were in good agreement with experimental results (Fig. 9). The detail analysis is available elsewhere².

where E, L, Glu, Gal, EL, EGal, EGlu and GOS represent the enzyme, lactose, glucose, galactose, enzyme-lactose, en-

zyme-galactose, enzyme-glucose, and combined GOS (tri- and tetra-saccharides), respectively. The k values are the apparent rate constants for the individual reactions.

Conclusion

The paper summarizes two earlier studies on synthesis and characterization of thermo-responsive bioconjugate and its application for the production of GOS. The bioconjugates showed much higher thermal and storage stability for longer periods of time without losing much initial activity as compared to the native enzyme. Moreover, the activities of both the PA β G and PN β G bioconjugates were less sensitive to pH variation than the native forms. The activity of PN β G bioconjugate and native enzyme was increased with addition of EG without any loss in stability; however, addition of ethanol decreased the stability. GOS was synthesized from lactose using PN β G bioconjugate. It was observed that GOS formation increased with increasing ILC for a slight decrease in yield of GOS after reaching maxima was noticed. As the enzyme concentration increased, the rate of formation of GOS was found to increase. However, the GOS at equilibrium state increased and eventually attained a plateau beyond a certain conjugated protein concentration. The PN β G bioconjugate showed a much better opportunity for reutilization in successive runs (>10 runs).

Notations and abbreviations

EG	Ethylene glycol
GOS	Galacto-oligosaccharides
ILC	Initial lactose concentration
LCST	Lower critical solution temperature
NIPAAm	<i>N</i> -Isopropyl acrylamide
ONPG	<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl- β -D-galactopyranoside
PAAm	Poly-acrylamide
PNIPAAm	Poly- <i>N</i> -isopropyl acrylamide
PA β G	Poly-acrylamide- β -galactosidase
PN β G	Poly- <i>N</i> -isopropyl acrylamide- β -galactosidase

Fig. 9. Validation of experimental values (symbols) and model simulated results (lines) for 200 g/L of initial lactose concentration and 0.275 mg/mL of conjugated protein (close symbols and solid lines); and for 100 g/L of initial lactose concentration and 0.275 mg/mL of conjugated protein (open symbols and dotted lines) at pH 6.0 and 40°C.

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